

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING DIVERGENT THINKING IN STUDENTS OF HIGHER MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the methods used in medical higher education institutions to teach students divergent thinking and to direct them to the profession in order to strengthen their further activities. In the new Uzbekistan, the features of raising young people to be educated and thinking at a high level and improving their psychology have been revealed.

Divergent thinking is a thinking process or method used to generate creative ideas by exploring multiple possible solutions. This usually happens in a spontaneous, free-flowing, non-linear way, so many ideas are generated in an emergent cognitive style. In a short period of time, many possible solutions are explored and unexpected connections are drawn. After divergent thinking, ideas and information are organized and structured using convergent thinking, which follows a specific set of logical steps to arrive at a single solution, which in some cases is the correct solution.

Psychologist J.P. Guilford first coined the terms convergent thinking and divergent thinking in 1956.

Activities that encourage divergent thinking include creating a list of questions, taking time for reflection and meditation, brainstorming, topic mapping, bubble mapping, journaling, tabletop role-playing, creating artwork, and free writing. In freewriting, a person focuses on a specific topic and writes about it in a short, stream-of-consciousness manner.

Different people live on earth. Naturally, everyone's thinking will be different and unique. Someone explains the incident in detail, while another immediately analyzes it. One gives different solutions to the problem, while the other solves a "concrete" puzzle. So, thinking is the inexhaustible stages of thinking of a person. As Franz Kafka, a Jewish writer from Prague, said, it is absurd to stop a person from thinking...

What kind of thinking do you like or how do you think? How to actually think? Have you ever heard of Divergent and Convergent Thinking? No? Then interesting information for you!

Joy Paul Gilford is an American psychologist and professor who teaches at many American universities. Known as the creator of the cognitive structure model. Gilford was involved in research on intelligence in terms of memory, reasoning, attention, creativity, and temperament. For the first time, the concept of "Divergent and Convergent thinking" was

introduced to psychology by J. Entered by Gilford. Also, this form of human brain activity makes it possible to change the main methods of problem solving, says the professor.

Divergent thinking (lat. divergere - separation) is a method of creative thinking, which is usually used in solving problems and tasks. It consists of finding many solutions to the same problem.

Convergent thinking (Lat. convergere - convergence) is based on the strategy of clearly using pre-learned algorithms to solve a specific problem, that is, instructions are given on the sequence and content of elementary operations to solve this problem.

Divergent thinking has four main characteristics: Fluency - the ability to quickly formulate several ideas and solutions; Non-standard - the ability to form ideas that have not occurred to others; Adaptability - the ability to think about different ways to solve a problem at the same time; Expertise is not thinking about the details of an idea, but the ability to find its embodiment.

Convergent thinking is often used in conjunction with divergent thinking. Convergent thinking emphasizes speed, accuracy, and logic, and focuses on recognizing, re-using, and retrieving stored information. Convergent thinking is also related to knowledge, as it involves the "manipulation" of existing knowledge using standard "procedures". An important aspect of convergent thinking is that it leads to a single best answer and leaves no room for uncertainty. After the divergent thinking process is completed, ideas and information are organized and structured using convergent thinking and decision-making strategies are applied, leading to a single best or most correct answer.

As a result of this, due to the individual's lack of success in his work, he cannot contribute to the development of the society and may even delay the development. The diagnosis of innate abilities and abilities shown at the lowest level of the pyramid is entrusted to the experts of psychological science. Features of studying the interest, abilities and skills of a person in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This activity is basically a process defined by the activity of the "Students Vocational Orientation and Psychological-Pedagogical Diagnosis Center" under the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

The main goal of our article was to develop divergent thinking in medical students. In order to do this faster, it is inevitable that a person will develop the ability to think about himself. After all, if the hidden abilities of the Uzbek people find their place of confirmation and effective use, it will not be far from the truth that it will lead to further development of our country.

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